

1 **Retinoid acid signaling during lineage commitment in the human embryo to the trophectoderm**
2 **(TE).**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of a
9 requirement for retinoid acid signaling in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human
10 embryo. This included important changes in Rai14 and Stra16.

11 Citations

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